

Separation Anxiety Disorder in Children

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To cite this article: PhD, Oya Kilic, Associate Professor Halise Heves Ozyilmaz, *Science*, Volume 5, No. 2-5, 2023, p. 01 – 39. - 0099-0001-2302-0101.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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Abstract

The issue is extreme anxiety, which is particularly damaging to youngsters and has the potential to cause widespread a. Anxiety of the many kinds, namely the one that... Separation anxiety disorder, which manifests as more often before infancy in phase recognized as an anxiety disorder variety part specified. Separation anxiety disorder in children will not occur in a manner that causes great fear and anxiety soon. This condition affects children who are inseparable from the people around them and who get attached to items throughout the course of their growth. It is quite common for youngsters to suffer from separation anxiety, which may manifest itself in both internal and outward orienting issues. The disease known as separation anxiety is compared to other forms of childhood and age-related anxiety disorders. Environmental variables are recognized to have a significant impact on the disorder. Half structured and responder-based meeting measurements, the child Separation anxiety disorder for diagnosis criteria meet and did not meet to decide about to widespread aspect used. at the child Separation anxiety disorder for diagnosis criteria meet and did not meet to decide about to widespread aspect used. The evaluation is the primary goal of this research, which focuses on children who suffer from separation anxiety disorder. This goal, by the literature review derived from the strategy that has been used. Literature review As a direct consequence of this, the owner has arrived at the following conclusion: the parent aspects a child's development of separation anxiety plays a key role in the overall impact.

Keywords: *Child, Separation Anxiety, Disorder*

1. Introduction

Excessive anxiety is a widespread issue that may negatively affect many aspects of young people's life, including their ability to function well in school and their ability for social adjustment. In the past, Separation Anxiety Condition (also known as SAD), which is one of the forms of anxiety, was thought of as a kind of anxiety disorder that manifests itself in infancy. On the other hand, several recent research (Battaglia, 2015; Bogels et al., 2013; Silove et al., 2015) have shown that adults may also suffer from seasonal affective disorder (SAD). SAD manifests itself in adults as feelings of isolation, which stem from childhood, may have an impact on adulthood, and begins in the late teen years or even later in life (Morrison, 2019).

According to Gümüş (2017), the symptoms of separation anxiety disorder in children include an inability to "separate from the person to whom they are attached, inability to move away from the objects to which they are attached, excessive fear and anxiety that is not appropriate for the developmental period." According to Işık and Taner (2006), the definition of separation anxiety is "experiencing the dread of separation or separation from the key person." SAD is characterized by a developmentally inappropriate fear of separation from caregivers or one's home that is excessive, persistent, distressing and disruptive and that lasts for at least four weeks. Additionally, SAD sufferers experience these symptoms in a manner that is excessive, persistent, distressing and disruptive (American Psychological Association, 2000). SAD is "marked by an exaggerated and excessive dread of separation from an attachment figure, generally a parent, that considerably interferes with day-to-day activities and developmental tasks," as said by Morris and March (2004:164).

The first manifestation of symptoms must have occurred before to the age of 18, and they cannot be ascribed to another disease on Axis I, a general medical condition, or the side effects of a drug (American Psychological Association, 2000). It is a normal developmental stage that is typical of children between the ages of 0 and 1, and it shows the state of emphasis on separation from the mother or other caregiver. Separation anxiety occurs in infants between the ages of 0 and 1. Around the age of one, children begin to display symptoms of separation anxiety, which typically last until they are around two and a half years old. One of the issues that should be investigated further is separation anxiety that lasts longer than this amount of time. According to Altınbaş (2009), maladaptation in children may begin around the age of 3, even if the kid's

concerns and anxieties do not persist at an excessive level. However, if this intensity continues, the child will develop maladaptation.

The prevalence of SAD ranges from 0.7-12.9% in community samples and 11.4-33% in clinically referred samples. The average age at which symptoms of SAD first appear is estimated to be 7 years (Masi et al., 2001). The lifetime prevalence of SAD is 5.2% (Kessler et al., 2005). (Costello et al., 2004). Rates are much higher in children, with estimates ranging from 3 to 13% in community samples of children (Anderson et al., 1987; Cohen et al., 1993) compared to 1.8 to 2.4% in samples of teenagers (Bowen et al., 1990). This is significant because seasonal affective disorder (SAD) is most common in children aged seven to twelve (Compton et al., 2000), but it may also create issues in adolescence and can continue throughout one's life if it is not treated throughout childhood. According to the findings of Shear et al. (2006), one-third of children diagnosed with SAD continue to have clinically severe SAD throughout adulthood. When prevalent in teenagers, seasonal affective disorder is linked to the initiation and continued development of adjustment issues, eating disorders, and depressive disorders (Ollendick et al., 1993).

According to Büküşoğlu (2004), fears and anxieties that are experienced during formative years might later develop as "fear of being kidnapped, dread of thieves, and fear of losing loved ones" in adult life. The most prevalent worries about separation include personal safety and harm (Silverman et al., 1995), being alone and sleeping alone, and being separated from a significant other (Farach , 2002).

Children affected by SAD are more likely to be disruptive in the classroom (Egger et al., 2003). There is a potential for school refusal behavior in up to seventy-five percent of children diagnosed with SAD (Masi et al., 2001). "an estimated 75% of children with SAD demonstrate school refusal behavior," the authors of Grover et al(2006: 's 279) study note. Based on his research on youngsters who do not have a desire to go to school, Broadwin (1932) supplied an explanation for separation anxiety under the heading "skipping school and not wanting to go to school." This circumstance may lead to undesirable outcomes such as "disobeying regulations, behaving defiantly, and being involved in criminal activity." The author underlined in his investigations that this circumstance does not show dread of school, and that children run away from school because of concern that something will happen to their moms rather than out of fear that they would be bullied at school.

It has been shown that children who have both internalizing and externalizing issues are more likely to suffer from separation anxiety (Weems et al., 2000). Separation anxiety is also strongly comorbid with depression; around one third of children suffer from both depressive disorder and SAD (Last, 1991). Additionally, a large comorbidity rate exists between SAD and other anxiety disorders. According to Masi et al. (1999), about one-third of children suffer from both seasonal affective disorder (SAD) and generalized anxiety disorder (GAD). These two illnesses have many symptoms in common.

The purpose of this investigation is to investigate the phenomenon of separation anxiety disorder in young children. A procedure known as "literature review" was used to conduct this goal.

2. Etiology

There are several different ideas about the elements that contribute to the development and maintenance of seasonal affective disorder (SAD). Most currently accepted ideas propose that seasonal affective disorder (SAD) results from the combination of many biological and environmental variables. Potential risk factors for seasonal affective disorder (SAD) include behavioral and biological vulnerabilities, as well as a hereditary predisposition to feel anxiety (Goldsmith & Gottesman, 1981). On the other hand, evidence shows that seasonal affective disorder (SAD), in comparison to other types of pediatric anxiety disorders, may be considerably impacted by environmental variables (Eley, 2001).

In the Virginia Twin Study of Adolescent Behavioral Development (VTSABD), anxiety symptoms in 1412 same-sex twin pairs between the ages of 8 and 16 were evaluated with the use of reports from both the children and their parents. The findings showed that the variation in child-reported SAD was attributed to both shared and non-shared environmental variables, and that there was no substantial genetic effect. In addition, the findings showed that there was no association between shared environmental factors and SAD (Topolski et al., 1997). On the other hand, the findings of a separate research that included the same-sex twin pairings of 2043 children aged 3 to 18 years showed evidence of shared environmental as well as genetic impacts on SAD (Feigon et al., 1997). When considered as a whole, these data imply that environmental variables have a significant role in the development of seasonal affective disorder (SAD) (Vasey & Dadds, 2001).

The actions of one's parents are often identified as one of the environmental elements that might contribute to the development of anxiety in children. There is a correlation between a lack of parental warmth and parental practices that impede autonomy, which has been linked to the development of anxiety as well as other developmental issues (Ginsburg et al., 2004). Research in developmental psychology and attachment theory has repeatedly revealed that insecure or anxious attachment styles are risk factors for many types of emotional disturbance and psychopathology, including depression, anxiety, and behavioral issues. (Westen et al., 2006). In addition, research shows that the locus of control has an etiological function, in the sense that early childhood events that encourage an external locus of control or a feeling of control over one's surroundings may be a risk factor for the development of anxiety. (Chorpita & Barlow, 1998).

Behaviors shown by parents that are too protective and overly engaged in their children's lives also play a vital part in the development and maintenance of anxiety in children. In addition, it seems that a special risk factor for SAD among children who have been diagnosed with anxiety disorders is the intrusiveness of their parents. In this sense, intrusive parenting is characterized by excessive management of the child's emotions and actions as well as authoritarian decision-making. Providing an excessive amount of aid with the child's daily activities, such as dressing or the bedtime routine, is a generic form of parental intrusiveness. This prevents the child from engaging in and progressing in age-appropriate behaviors and activities, which can be detrimental to the child's development. These overbearing parental activities, which are intended to alleviate or prevent the child's suffering, may instead foster the child's dependency on the parents and, as a result, alter the child's beliefs of his or her position of power in relation to the surrounding environment (Wood et al., 2003).

3. Assessment of Separation Anxiety Disorder

It is widespread practice to employ interview measures that are semi-structured or respondent-based to set up whether a kid satisfies diagnostic criteria for SAD. The Anxiety Disorders Interview Schedule for DSM-IV, Child and Parent Version (ADIS-IV-C/P; Silverman & Albano, 1996) is the diagnostic interview that is most widely used for the evaluation of seasonal affective disorder (SAD). The ADIS-IV-C/P is a semi-structured interview that has been shown to be useful in diagnosing children with a variety of anxiety disorders, including generalized

anxiety disorder (GAD), obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), social phobia, specific phobias, and SAD. In addition, it has been shown to be useful in diagnosing children with mood disorders. Good to outstanding test-retest reliability is one of the great psychometric features that the ADIS-IV-C/P has for the purpose of finding anxiety disorders (Silverman et al., 2001), and there is evidence to support the convergent validity of the test as well (Wood et al., 2002). This interview is used often in the diagnostic evaluation of children who suffer from anxiety disorders (Silverman et al., 2001). Separate interviews with the child and the parent are conducted, and a combination of the information gained from each is used to construct a diagnosis (Silverman and Nelles, 1988). This evaluation method enables the clinician to collect specific information about the child's presenting symptoms, such as frequency, severity, and duration, from the point of view of both the kid and the parents. This information may then be used to formulate a treatment plan.

Other diagnostic interviews that are widely used include the Schedule for Affective Disorders and Schizophrenia for School-Age Children-Present and Lifetime version (K-SADS-PL; Kaufman et al., 1999) and the Diagnostic Interview Schedule for Children, Version IV. Both interviews measure SAD symptoms and other forms of childhood psychopathology in a more comprehensive manner (DISC-IV; Shaffer et al., 2000). The K-SADS-PL is a diagnostic interview that is semi-structured, and it evaluates present and historical episodes of psychopathology in children and adolescents using criteria from the DSM-III-R and the DSM-IV. Likewise, the DISC-IV and its computerized equivalent, the C-DISC, are both highly structured, respondent-based interviews meant to be conducted by lay interviewers for the purpose of deciding whether children and adolescents have common psychiatric illnesses.

3.1. Assessment of Preschool Age Children

Most anxiety assessment tools for children have been created and confirmed for children of school age; hence, early childhood problems are still relatively understudied. Understanding of the etiology and developmental trajectory of early psychopathology, as well as the efficacy of early therapeutic intervention, has been hampered by the lack of adequate diagnostic instruments for young children. This has led to a lack of progress in the field (Egger & Angold, 2006). Early detection and treatment of seasonal affective disorder (SAD) is essential given that the onset of SAD symptoms often occurs before the age of six and that these symptoms in

early childhood are associated to later psychopathology. Researchers have spent the last several years attempting to set up diagnostic criteria and evaluation tools for preschool-aged children (Task Force on Research Diagnostic Criteria, 2003).

In addition, a limited number of clinical interviews have been designed as part of an attempt to get a deeper comprehension of the manifestations of psychopathology in young children. For instance, the Preschool Age Mental Assessment (PAPA; Egger et al., 1999) is an example of a structured parent interview that is used to evaluate psychiatric illnesses in children who are between the ages of two and five years old. The Child and Adolescent Psychiatric Assessment serves as the foundation for the Pediatric Adaptation of the Child and Adolescent Psychiatric Assessment (PAPA), which has been changed in both structure and content to make it suitable for use with incredibly young children. The PAPA is the first developmentally proper structured psychiatric interview designed to assess psychopathology, family and community risk factors, as well as resilience and protective factors in community and clinical samples of preschool children younger than two years of age. The PAPA was developed to assess psychopathology, family and community risk factors, as well as resilience and protective factors.

3.2. Self-Report Measures

Diagnostic interview measures are often regarded as the "gold standard" for supplying a correct and exhaustive evaluation of DSM-IV criteria for SAD; nevertheless, these interviews are typically time-consuming, expensive, and need some amount of professional training to conduct. Self-report measures may also be obtained from parents and children in the evaluation of SAD. This is possible even when there is less time and less resources available, provided that the kid has the reading and/or writing abilities necessary to reply properly to such surveys. Although these methods have shown promise in the evaluation and later treatment of children who suffer from separation anxiety and concern, they should not be used on their own to make a diagnosis of SAD.

The Multidimensional Anxiety Scale for Children (MASC; March et al., 1997) is an experimentally produced, multidomain self-report scale that consists of 39 items. Its purpose is to evaluate a broad variety of anxiety symptoms in children. Tense/Anxious, Somatic/Autonomic, Total Physical Symptoms, Perfectionism, Anxious Coping, Total Harm Avoidance, Humiliation/Rejection, Performance Fears, Total Social Anxiety, Separation/Panic,

and Total MASC score are the subscales that are included in the MASC. A more concise, ten-item version of the MACS is also available (MASC-10). Given the high rates of comorbidity among children and adolescents who suffer from SAD, GAD, OCD, and other anxiety disorders, the MASC's capacity to evaluate a broad variety of anxiety symptoms is extremely helpful (Curry et al., 2004).

The DSM-IV diagnostic criteria are used to inform the development of the 34-item Separation Anxiety Assessment Scale, Parent and Child Versions (SAAS-C/P; Eisen & Schaefer, 2007). This scale examines features of children separation anxiety disorder (SAD) and accompanying anxiety symptoms. The SAAS evaluates four different symptom dimensions: worry about catastrophic events, fear of physical illness, fear of being alone, and fear of being abandoned. In addition to that, the SAAS consists of a subscale for the frequency of catastrophic events as well as an index for safety signals.

The Spence Kid Anxiety Scale (SCAS; Spence, 1997) measures a child's level of anxiety by obtaining information from both the child and the parent. The scale can measure a broad spectrum of anxiety symptoms, has a special factor/scale that evaluates separation anxiety symptoms, and offers information on added symptoms associated with anxiety disorders. The following types of anxiety are measured on the subscales: separation anxiety, panic/agoraphobia, social anxiety, generalized anxiety, obsessions/compulsions, and fear of being physically hurt. Confirmatory factor analysis was used to decide the scale structure of the SCAS, which consists of six subscales (Spence, 1998).

Self-reporting is needed for children less than seven years old to complete the Screen for Child Anxiety Related Emotional Disorders-Revised (SCARED-R; Muris et al., 1999) questionnaire. There is also a parent version of this scale that may be used. There are 66 questions on the SCARED-R that measure anxiety disorders in children and adolescents according to the DSM-IV, and there are 8 questions that specifically evaluate SAD.

3.3. Assessment of Parent-Child Interaction

Interactional elements between parents and their children have been known to have a role in both the development and continuation of anxiety disorders in children for a long time. As a result, direct observation of behavior is of utmost importance and value when conducting a full psychological evaluation, particularly of youngsters (McMahon & Forehand, 1988). Such

observation is also important since self-report assessments sometimes yield inadequate data, which is particularly problematic when evaluating improper behaviors like avoidant behavior, which is typical of children who have SAD (Hartmann & Wood, 1990). Even though behavioral observation protocols are not diagnostic tools, they do give an evaluation of interaction elements that are hypothesized to contribute to SAD in childhood as well as reactions from parents and children to situations in which they are separated. The clinical community now has access to a method for evaluating parent-child interactions that is based on direct observation thanks to the development of the Dyadic Parent-Child Interaction Coding System (DPICS; Eyberg & Robinson, 1983) and the later Dyadic Parent-Child Interaction Coding System II (DPICS II; Eyberg et al., 1994). Both systems were created by Eyberg and Robinson. It is of the utmost importance to treat interactions of this kind in children who suffer from separation anxiety because interactions of this nature, when they are maladaptive, set up the fundamental structure of the condition.

DPICS II covers behavioral categories for both the parent and the child, such as behavioral descriptions, informative descriptions, inquiries, instructions, and labeled as well as unlabeled praise and criticism. The DPICS II is conducted by a predetermined protocol, and it consists of three stages of a condensed play interaction between the child and the parent. During the first phase, which is referred to as Kid-Directed Interaction (CDI), the child is encouraged to play directly while the parent works to set up a good atmosphere that is non-directive. During the second part of the interaction, known as the Parent-Directed Interaction or PDI for short, the parent will take charge of directing the play. During the last stage, known as "Cleanup" or "CU," the youngster must tidy up the playroom (Eyberg et al., 1994).

Recent changes were made to DPICS II and its coding system to make it more suitable for usage with young children who suffer from separation anxiety and the families of such children (Pincus et al., 2006). The counselor is aware of the sorts of behaviors the kid may display during acute separation times by adding a fourth observational phase called "Separation," during which the parent momentarily leaves the room, and the child is recommended to play with a confidant. The DPICS II, in its modified form for use with children who suffer from separation anxiety, may be beneficial not only for diagnosing the condition but also for tracking treatment's progression, deciding its effectiveness, and ensuring that the patient continues to improve over time.

4. Parent and Child Reporting Differences

Inconsistencies have been found in parent and child accounts of issues affecting children and adolescents when doctors conduct assessments of these patients' conditions (Briggs-Gowan et al., 1996). Studies conducted by experts have revealed that internalizing actions and symptoms are more likely to be inconsistent than externalizing behaviors and symptoms (Achenbach et al., 1987). One of the possible explanations for the disparity in the accounts provided by the kid and the parent is the presence of psychopathology in one or both of the parties. The researchers Moretti and colleagues (1985) showed that depressive symptoms in parents were positively correlated with their children's feelings of being depressed. According to the findings of another research, moms who reported higher levels of depression were more likely to see their children as having a poor adjustment (Griest et al., 1979).

Schaughency and The Hague (1985) discovered more evidence that showed that maternal depression was a substantial independent predictor of the mother reporting externalizing issues in each child. According to the comments of the children's parents, Frick et al. (1994) discovered that 76% of children with anxiety disorders had a mother with an earlier diagnosis of anxiety disorder. Seventy-three percent of women who suffer from anxiety disorders said that their children also suffered from the condition. In addition, both the parent and the kid reported feelings of worry in the youngster, and these feelings were linked to a history of anxiety in the mother. Researchers Briggs-Gowen and colleagues (1996) discovered that mother anxiety and depression were related with greater levels of maternal reports of child symptomatology than those reported by the child or teacher. Krain and Kendall (2000) discovered a substantial connection between depressed symptoms experienced by mothers and the reports of their children experiencing anxiety. On the other hand, it is essential to bear in mind that adults who seek therapy for their anxiety are more likely to report experiencing more symptoms than their children are. According to the research conducted by Biedel and Turner (1998), anxious children in general report less symptoms and less discomfort than their parents do.

According to Bogels and van Melick (2004), there is also a low level of agreement in the accounts of parenting actions made by parents and children. According to Bogels et al(2001) .'s research, children report having less healthy parenting than their parents. According to the findings of one research (Bogels & van Melick, 2004), women had a more favorable image of

their own parenting methods as well as the behaviors of their spouses as compared to the reports provided by their children and partners. As a result, the mother's account can understate the extent to which she engages in maladaptive parenting, potentially owing to the management of good impressions. According to Bogels and Brechman-Toussaint (2006), anxious children may also be more sensitive to the feeling of rejection, leading them to interpret their parents' conduct as being more hostile. Similarly, one research revealed that children's anxiety symptoms were better predicted by their judgments of their dads' parenting practices than their assessments of their mothers' parenting activities (van Brakel & Muris, 2006).

5. The Relationship between Child and Parental Anxiety

When compared to children who do not have any psychological problems, research has revealed that parents of children who have anxiety disorders have a greater incidence of anxiety disorders, mood disorders, and drug use disorders. Studies on families have showed that there is an increased risk of anxiety disorders in children whose parents suffer from anxiety disorders (Biedel & Turner, 1998). Likewise, studies have showed that the incidence of anxiety disorders among the parents of children who have anxiety disorders is higher than the incidence of anxiety disorders in the general population (Last et al., 1991).

Turner et al. (1987) found that children of patients with anxiety disorders were more anxious and fearful and had more somatic complaints compared to children of parents without disorders and children of parents with dysthymic disorders. They also found that children of parents with anxiety disorders had more somatic complaints than children of parents without disorders. In addition, this relationship was discovered in a variety of demographic types. In a community-based sample of one hundred African American parents and their biological children, Chapman et al. (2012) discovered that children who had an anxious parent were four times more likely to meet the criteria for anxiety disorder as well as other types of psychopathology. The sample consisted of both biological and adoptive families.

The fact that certain forms of anxiety illness are shared between parents and their offspring may be attributed to several varied factors. The first possibility is that it is passed down via genetics. Studies on genetics have showed that the heritability of an anxiety propensity might be as high as fifty percent. This can be related to a variety of variables, including behavioral inhibition, anxiety sensitivity, and the fear of being negatively evaluated (Stein et al., 2002). However, the

heredity of mental illnesses, and particularly anxiety disorders, is close to thirty percent (Kendler et al., 1992). It is important to keep in mind that the emergence of anxiety is likely influenced by the interaction of genetic factors as well as family behavioral factors. These factors include the reinforcement and modeling of anxiety responses due to the anxiety of other family members. Although anxiety and anxiety proneness are inherited, it is important to keep in mind that the emergence of anxiety is likely influenced by the interaction of these factors. The fact that youngsters see their parents stressed out may play a role in the development of the child's own anxious feelings. Even after accounting for mother trait anxiety, Muris et al. (1996) discovered a substantial positive correlation between parental cowardice and child cowardice. This was the case even if the researchers controlled for the maternal characteristic. Importantly, modeling anxious behavior is likely a mediator of this relationship; children of mothers who express fear have the highest levels of fear, and fear expression uniquely explains some of the variance in children's fearfulness. Children have the highest levels of fear when compared to children of mothers who do not express fear.

6. Attachment and Anxiety

Attachment, which refers to the link that exists between children and their parents, may be another factor that relates to anxious symptomatology. According to the findings of several studies, the degree to which a kid believes that his or her caregiver is present and easy to reach to supply protection and solace is related to the level of anxiety that the child experiences. There are three distinct forms of insecure attachment that can affect children: anxious-avoidant attachment (does not need and rejects close relationships), anxious-ambivalent attachment (preoccupied and anxious with relationships due to caregiver inconsistency; (Ainsworth et al., 1978), and disorganized attachment (both anxious-avoidant attachment and disorganized attachment are considered to be forms of "anxious attachment" (Bogels & Brechman - Toussaint, Crowell and Feldman (1991) discovered that stressed moms had trouble parting from their children and, as a result, were unable to adequately prepare their children for the upcoming separation. The children of these moms are the ones that display the highest levels of anxiety prior to the separation. When they were reunited after being apart for some time, anxious and indifferent moms, along with their children, avoided social engagement. Researchers Manassis

and colleagues (1995) saw that children of mothers who suffered from anxiety disorders had greater rates of insecure attachment and behavioral inhibition. According to the findings of Warren and colleagues (1997), children who showed behavioral inhibition and insecure attachment were more likely to develop anxiety disorders than children who showed behavioral inhibition and secure attachment.

In addition to the kid's impression of control, Rapee (2001) and Barlow (2002) underlined that the child's sense of autonomy and personal competence also modulate the impact of family circumstances on child anxiety. Thus, children with disorganized attachment may feel that their environment is uncontrollable because of their parents' excessive and unpredictable behaviors; anxious-ambivalent children may not be allowed to use their autonomy and personal competence because of excessive parental attention and separation problems; anxious-avoidant attached children may develop a negative view of themselves and fear of negative evaluation as a result of rejection experiences (Bogels & Brechman -Toussain). These findings were published in Bogels & Brechman-Tous

A secure attachment to the father may protect the child from social anxiety, while attachment to the mother may be more related to separation anxiety due to the mother's role as the primary caregiver of the child. Bogels and Brechman-Toussaint (2006) suggested that since father-child attachment is related to whether the child develops anxious social behaviors, the father may play a stronger role in introducing the child to the world outside the family.

7. Parental Behaviors and Beliefs

There is some evidence that suggests that excessive parental control may be a contributory factor in the onset of anxiety in children. The term "parental overcontrol" refers to the practice of parents excessively regulating, checking, and intervening in the conduct of their children, which discourages the children from independently finding solutions to problems. According to Bogels and Brechman-Toussaint (2006), these actions are considered to restrict the kid's autonomy, lead the child to believe that the environment is unpredictable, and produce a diminished feeling of the child's own personal competence. It is believed that the kid's limited personal competence and the child's feeling that he or she has little influence over the child's surroundings both contribute to the development of anxiety in the child (Barlow, 2002).

Two studies that looked at the research on the topic (Rapee, 1997 and Wood et al., 2003) came to the same conclusion: there is a connection between excessive control and child distress. Bogels and van Melick (2004), using a method based on many information methods, came to the same conclusions as prior researchers: that there is a connection between parental overcontrol and child distress. Several research have used observational data to investigate nervous children and have discovered evidence showing a connection between elevated levels of parental control and lower levels of child anxiety (Greco & Morris, 2002).

Negativity in the kid's surroundings is also considered to effect child anxiety; negative feedback may lead children to feel as if their environment is hostile and scary, which can hinder their feeling of competence and raise their expectations of poor outcomes (Krohne & Hock, 1991). A lack of affection and acceptance from parents, as well as criticism and/or hostility directed toward the kid, are all symptoms of negative parenting (Wood, et al., 2003).

According to the findings of Rapee (1997) and Wood et al. (2003), the evidence on the relationship between child anxiety and a lack of warmth and acceptance in the family is conflicting. Bogels and van Melick (2004) discovered that the association between child anxiety and parental overcontrol was much stronger than the relationship between parental warmth and child anxiety. Two studies that relied on observational techniques came to the same conclusion: there is a connection between a mother's warmth and acceptance and her child's level of anxiety (Hudson & Rapee , 2001; Moore, et al., 2004). There was no significant difference found between children who suffered from elevated levels of social anxiety and children who suffered from low levels of social anxiety in terms of the amount of negativity shown by their dads (Greco & Morris, 2002).

Although parental overcontrol and negativity are often examined in isolation from one another, recent research has revealed that the interplay of the two, namely high control and low warmth, may be the strongest predictor of child anxiety. (Parker, 1990). According to Bogels and Brechman-Toussaint (2006), the absence of warmth may not have a significant impact on anxiety on its own; but the absence of warmth may combine with parental control to cause worry in children.

It was guessed by Bogels and Brechman-Toussiant (2006) as well that the link between these elements could not be as linear as is often believed to be the case. Instead, there may be a relationship that is more like a curvilinear one, in which less parental control leads to an

excessive amount of autonomy at an inappropriately early age, and more parental control leads to an inappropriate loss of autonomy by the child, both of which result in anxiety at opposite ends of the spectrum. Similarly, children who are not accepted by their parents develop feelings of insecurity and anxiety, while children who receive an excessive amount of acceptance from their parents may become more accommodating and allow the child to avoid and withdraw from uncomfortable situations. This leads to continued anxiety in the child. In addition, it is not known if having one parent who is warm and welcoming may make up for the absence of warmth and acceptance from the other parent, and whether this can thus run as a protective factor against the development of anxiety.

The views that parents have about their children's anxious reactions influence how the parents respond to their children's anxious behaviors. Even after controlling for parental anxiety and depression, researchers discovered that dysfunctional parental beliefs about child anxiety and parenting self-efficacy were positively associated with child anxiety. This was the case even though the researchers took parental anxiety and depression into account (Herren et al., 2013). The research conducted by Francis and Chorpita (2011) found that parental beliefs that child anxiety is significantly harmful mediated the relationship between parent and child anxiety. This finding suggests that parents' negative beliefs about their child's anxiety (i.e., that their child's anxiety is harmful) influence whether their own anxiety is related to their child's anxious symptoms. According to the findings of one research, parents were less likely to support their children's independence when they were four years old if they thought their two-year-olds were timid (Rubin et al., 1999).

It was discovered that mothers of highly anxious children aged four were more likely to attribute their child's social withdrawal to their child's temperament, to respond to their child's withdrawal with negative emotions, to believe that anxious behavior would be difficult to change, and to act in a more directive and overcontrolling manner in order to deal with their child's anxious behavior (Mills & Rubin, 1993). Except for the overcontrolled management method, Mills and Rubin (1993) found the same response pattern in a sample of moms of nine-year-old nervous children compared to their non-anxious peers of the same age. In contrast, these moms did not react in any way to the worried behaviors shown by their children. According to Bogels and Brechman-Toussaint (2006), moms of nervous children may, over the course of time, buy a learned helplessness that stops them from thinking that their children's

behaviors can change, and as a result, they do not try to influence their children's responses. The kid does not learn how to create a feeling of personal control over tough circumstances whether the parent reacts by being too controlling or by allowing the child to engage in avoidance behavior (Barlow, 2002).

8. Somatic Symptoms

In children, painful physical symptoms including headaches, chest discomfort, and stomach pain are common and may be quite disruptive to their lives. Recurrent stomach pain has a high incidence of 10-15%, particularly in school-age children (Faull and Nicol, 1986). Similarly, non-cardiac chest pain has a prevalence that ranges from 7-15% in community samples (Campo & Nicol, 1986), according to Fritsch (1994). According to the findings of a comprehensive epidemiological research, 10% of youngsters suffer from headaches on a weekly basis (Egger et al., 1998). Because children who suffer from somatic symptoms must go to school, there has been shown to be a considerable impairment in functioning in both the academic and social domains (Martin- Herz et al., 1999).

It is quite uncommon for a medical or biological etiology to be discovered for these somatic problems. After testing, there is often no conclusive medical explanation for why the symptoms continue to exist over the course of years. These families often seek doctors to discover an explanation for the discomfort that their kid is experiencing (Zavaras-Angelidou et al., 1992). Some of the symptoms include an overwhelming fear that they or their parents would suffer damage if they were separated from each other and that they might not ever be able to find one other again (Morris & March 2004: 164). According to Kendall et al. (1992:4), "indicators of SAD include: calling their mother frequently from school or stopping play frequently to check on their parent, not being able to be left with a babysitter because they object too strongly, worrying so often about the mother's health that they try to make sure the parent is taking their medication, waiting at the mailbox, crying for the parent to return, and refusing to go to sleepovers or camp with friends." In other words, children who show these behaviors According to Grover et al. (2006), children with SAD show several other frequent behaviors, such as a reluctance to be alone, a rejection to sleep alone, or a hesitation to address school. These are just few examples. According to McLoone et al. (2006: 222), the time of day when "separation

anxiety is most typically reported at the beginning of the school day, when the parent leaves the kid at school" is "when the parent leaves the child at school."

According to Egger et al. (1999), there is a strong correlation between internalizing illnesses and somatic complaints; fifty percent of individuals who have unexplained somatic symptoms also fit the criteria for anxiety or mood disorders (Simon et al., 1996).

Because of this, medically unexplained somatic symptoms may be well described by anxiety disorders and mood disorders (Husain et al., 2007). More than half of the yearly expense of anxiety disorders in the United States is accounted for by medical treatments that are not psychiatric in nature (Greenberg, et al., 1999). Therefore, bodily symptoms generate a considerable deal of suffering and need medical attention in anxious children and adults.

Children and adolescents diagnosed with SAD have also been shown to have symptoms of panic. Anxiety episodes are defined by a time of great dread accompanied by four or more symptoms (such as palpitations, sweating, shaking, and shortness of breath) that begin quickly and reach their height within ten minutes. Panic attacks may be life-threatening. Early adulthood is the normal onset time for panic disorder, which is defined by recurring panic attacks, changes in behavior to prevent panic attacks, and the dread of having new attacks. Panic disorder may also be characterized by a fear of having new attacks (Burke et al., 1990). Anxiety disorders may cause panic attacks, which often take place in response to stimuli that are known to be anxiety-inducing. According to the findings of Masi et al. (2000), 73% of youngsters (7-18 years old) who suffered from panic attacks also suffered from an antecedent or linked case of separation anxiety. During times of separation, children could also suffer signs of panic (Garland & Smith, 1991). It is important to note that the panic that children and adolescents experience during separation is triggered by separation anxiety, not "out of the blue" recurrent panic attacks or anxiety about future attacks. This distinction is important because it helps explain why children and adolescents experience panic during separation.

Children who are less than 12 years old often do not show signs of concern about the potential outcomes of panic attacks, such as passing away, losing control, or having a heart attack (Kearney & Silverman, 1992). It is easy to see why young infants the cognitive development does not have necessary for making this sort of relationship because of this. When it comes to young children, the symptoms of anxiety that manifest themselves physically are more common than the cognitive ones. Therefore, they experience bodily manifestations of their anxiety, such

as stomach discomfort and hyperventilation; nevertheless, the implications of or attributions for their physical manifestations of worry are not well understood. Before having a panic attack, people with panic disorder may show various somatic symptoms and even hypochondriacal thinking, according to the findings of several research (Schmidt et al., 1997).

9. Treatment of Separation Anxiety Disorder

Effective therapies for juvenile anxiety disorders have just been developed and studied in the last 20 years, even though these conditions are among the most frequent types of developmental psychopathology. Currently, cognitive behavior therapy (CBT; Velting et al., 2004) is the treatment that has the greatest evidence supporting its efficacy in treating anxiety disorders in children, including seasonal affective disorder (SAD). The goal of cognitive behavior therapy (also known as CBT) is to aid anxious people to better deal with their anxiety by reducing their level of anxiety via the use of exposure methods and cognitive restructuring. In addition, cognitive behavioral therapy often incorporates psychoeducation on the causes and treatments of anxiety, as well as strategies for reducing anxiety, such as progressive muscle relaxation and breathing retraining. Although cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) has been shown to be beneficial in treating anxiety problems in children and adolescents in several controlled trials (Kendall et al., 1997), most of these research have omitted children less than seven years old. Young individuals who suffer from anxiety disorders, such as SAD, often find success with the CBT intervention known as the Coping Cat program. The treatment begins with cognitive retraining and relaxation training, and then gradually introduces participants to circumstances that may trigger anxiety, during which time they practice coping strategies that they have bought in earlier sessions (Grover et al., 2006). A randomized controlled experiment (RCT; Kendall, 1994) with 47 children ranging in age from 8 to 13 years was used to evaluate the effectiveness of the Coping Cat program. Participants in the trial had to meet diagnostic criteria for social anxiety disorder, generalized anxiety disorder, or social phobia, and they were then randomly assigned to either a 16-week therapy or a waitlist control condition. According to the findings, the children who were given the treatment condition had much better results than those who were given the waiting assignment. Comparatively, after receiving therapy, just 5% of participants in the waiting list condition fulfilled the criteria for an anxiety disorder, while 66% of participants in the Coping Cat program no longer qualified the criteria for an anxiety disorder.

Evaluations of long-term follow-up at three and seven and a half years following therapy concluded that the benefits of the treatment lasted over time and were not lost. These encouraging findings were duplicated in a second randomized controlled trial (RCT) that included 94 nervous young kids ranging in age from nine to thirteen. Again, the participants were randomly distributed to either a waiting list control or the Coping Cat therapy program. After receiving therapy, more than half of the children and adolescents in the treatment group were able to overcome their main diagnosis (Kendall et al., 1997).

Because of the crucial part that parents play in keeping their children's separation anxieties alive, SAD treatment plans often call for the engagement of the whole family. The FRIENDS program is a cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) intervention for children with anxiety disorders that is provided in a group setting over the course of ten sessions (Barrett et al., 2000). The treatment incorporates not only the fundamental aspects of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), such as cognitive restructuring and systematic exposure, but also aspects of interpersonal therapy and family participation are essential. The program may, for instance, include cognitive restructuring for parents, and families may also be encouraged to create supportive social networks. It is strongly recommended that parents go through the FRIENDS skills with their children on a regular basis, offering positive reinforcement whenever the abilities are used in an acceptable manner. In addition to the significance of the involvement of parents, the program emphasizes the significance of the engagement of peers and the provision of interpersonal support. Particularly highlighted are the development of friendships, the discussion of challenging circumstances with friends, and the acquisition of knowledge from the experiences of peers.

FRIENDS is an abbreviation that stands for the following: F – Feelings; R – Remember to Relax, Have Quiet time; II – I can do my best (Inner Helpful Thoughts); E – Explore options and Coping Step Plans; N – Now reward yourself; D – Do it every day; and S – Smile! You are now aware of how to deal with this situation, so try to remain cool and communicate with support staff. An RCT was conducted using the FRIENDS program, and it included 71 children between the ages of six and ten who were diagnosed with social anxiety disorder (SAD), generalized anxiety disorder (GAD), or social phobia (Shortt et al., 2001). The subjects were distributed to either the treatment condition or the wait-list control condition using a random number generator. After receiving therapy, results revealed that 69 percent of children in the

FRIENDS program no longer fulfilled diagnostic criteria for anxiety disorder, compared to just 6 percent of children in the control group. At the one-year follow-up evaluation, the therapeutic benefits that had been achieved by study participants in the therapy group were still present.

As was just showed, participation from both the parent and the kid is often encouraged as part of the therapy for SAD. However, the findings of the early study point to the possibility that direct engagement of children is not needed. Eisen et al. (2008) conducted a research not too long ago in which they investigated the usefulness of an integrated cognitive-behavioral parent training intervention designed particularly for parents of children and adolescents with SAD. Six families were recruited, each with one kid (ranging in age from seven to ten years) who satisfies the diagnostic criteria for SAD. The research was conducted using a multiple baseline design. Traditional cognitive-behavioral strategies like as psychoeducation, in-session practice, imaginal exposure, and homework assignments were included into the therapy protocol throughout the course of the ten sessions that were reserved exclusively for the parents. After receiving the therapy, five of the six children who took part were no longer considered to have SAD while the sixth kid was classified with subclinical SAD. In addition to this, the intervention resulted in improvements that were statistically and clinically significant in terms of parental self-efficacy and stress.

As was showed previously, the majority of CBT research for childhood anxiety disorders, including SAD, has evaluated treatment results exclusively for children aged 7 or older. This is because CBT is generally considered to be more effective in treating these conditions in older children. Given the relatively more complicated cognitive and reasoning abilities that are necessary to master certain CBT techniques such as cognitive restructuring, it seems sense to impose this age restriction for practical reasons. However, due to the widespread usage of this age-based exclusion criteria, virtually little is known about effective therapies for young children who suffer from seasonal affective disorder (SAD). This is even though SAD symptoms often appear in children under the age of seven.

Relatively recently, Parent-Child Interaction Therapy (PCIT; Brinkmeyer & Eyberg, 2003) has been designed expressly for the treatment of SAD in young children (Pincus et al., 2005). Parent-Child Interaction Therapy was developed for the purpose of treating seasonal affective disorder (SAD) in children between the ages of four and eight years old. It consists of three treatment phases: Child Directed Interaction (CDI), Bravery Directed Interaction (BDI), and

Parent Directed Interaction (PDI). During the CDI phase, the primary emphasis is on enhancing the quality of the interaction between the parents and children. Interaction skills are taught to parents, with a particular emphasis placed on supplying parental warmth, attention, and praise. This, in turn, makes it easier for children to build their own internal attributions of self-control. The increased attachment and warmth that are induced by the CDI may aid to build the kid's feeling of security, which in turn promotes separation from the parent with less discomfort for the child. Differential reinforcement, often known as rewarding acceptable conduct while ignoring unruly behavior, is a constructive and efficient strategy for managing behavior. It involves praising good behavior and dismissing unpleasant behavior.

The Behavioral Distress Intervention (BDI) phase starts with psychoeducation for parents on the nature of anxiety and discusses the rationale for gradually exposing the anxious child to circumstances that generate separation anxiety. The therapist collaborates with the parent(s) and the kid to build a fear hierarchy or "bravery ladder" that finds each circumstance that the child fears and/or presently avoids. The goal of this project is to help the child overcome their fears and become more courageous. In addition, the family makes a list of potential prizes for the kid to work for to encourage positive conduct while confronting scary circumstances.

In the third stage of therapy, known as PDI, parents are educated on various strategies for effectively regulating their kid's misbehavior by combining age-appropriate instructions that may be properly expressed to the child. Parents are instructed to provide their children with consistent positive and negative consequences following the child's obedience and disobedience by using techniques that are based on operant principles of direct behavior change. These techniques can be found in behavioral modification programs. In addition to this, the therapist educates the parents on how the child's social environment contributes to the formation and maintenance of the child's behavior. For instance, parents may unknowingly promote anxious behaviors in their children by devoting extra attention to the youngster, which increases the possibility that the child will continue to show similar behaviors in the future (Eisen et al., 1998).

Throughout the course of PCIT's three stages, parents get active coaching on how to practice skills while engaging in a play activity with their kid. The coaching is done via a mirror that only looks in one direction, and an "in-ear listening device" (consisting of a walkie-talkie and a headset microphone) is used to interact with and advise the parents. The ability of the parents

to display a particular number of each skill while doing an observed interaction activity is what decides whether they have mastered the skills.

10. Conclusion

Following a review of the relevant research, the authors concluded that parental variables have a considerable impact on the likelihood that a kid would develop separation anxiety. Because anxiety influences the way parents interact with their children and how they behave in front of them, it has a ripple effect on the child's acquired information and behavior. Because anxiety may have detrimental long-term implications, particularly if it is not addressed, it is essential, for the sake of both prevention and therapy, to decide the process by which anxious behaviors shown by parents are triggered. There is a strong correlation between parental anxiety sensitivity and parental somatization, as well as the kid's knowledge of the anxiety experienced by the parent, and the likelihood that a child would buy SAD. Younger children often show more physical and physiological symptoms of anxiety than cognitive ones, and their levels of anxiety are likely to be significantly affected by the way in which they are modeled and interact with their caregivers. Because of this, it is of the utmost significance that these aspects be investigated and considered during care provided to young children. Like most illnesses that affect children, early diagnosis, educated criteria to estimate prognosis, and prompt treatment all carry a significant amount of weight in the fight against the burden and expense of SAD.

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